

Working Group 1 Inclusive &
Participatory Practices during AR6

RETROSPECTIVE EVALUATION

March 2023

by Shift Collaborative

www.shiftcollaborative.ca

shift to a
better world

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Acknowledgements: SHIFT Collaborative has been privileged to accompany the WGI authors, Bureau and TSU on their journey to strengthen diversity and inclusion throughout the AR6 process.

This work has been a collective, iterative effort and there have been many authors and other Working Group members who have contributed significantly to a deeper understanding of this work through their stories and experiments with new ways of working together. Our shared hope is that this report serves to support knowledge transfer and continued learning and improvement in AR7 and other future IPCC processes.

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7822894](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7822894)

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Executive Summary

Working Group I (WGI) of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change is responsible for assessing the physical science of climate change, most recently contributing to the IPCC's Sixth Assessment Report (AR6) between 2018 -2021. The Working Group engaged over 230 scientists from all parts of the world who collaborated and shared their expertise and knowledge to assess the latest knowledge on climate science and change. From the outset of AR6, WGI identified that encouraging the participation and inclusion of diverse authors within the Working Group could positively influence the quality and impact of the final assessment report and made efforts to support this.

Activities

Several activities were undertaken to strengthen participation and inclusion throughout the assessment process. These included: introducing a [Code of Conduct](#)¹ at the first lead author meeting (LAM1, 2018); running post-LAM surveys with authors which involved a range of evaluative questions about participation and inclusion; and working with [SHIFT Collaborative](#), beginning at LAM2 (2019) onwards to the end of the assessment process, to provide expert support for creating an inclusive and participatory culture. Together with the Bureau and Technical Support Unit (TSU), in the time surrounding LAM2, 3, and 4, SHIFT Collaborative designed resources and facilitated a series of training and dialogue opportunities for authors and facilitation training and coaching for Coordinating Lead Authors (CLAs).

Impacts, Lessons & Recommendations

This report, written by SHIFT Collaborative with input from the WGI TSU, summarizes key findings and learnings from a retrospective evaluation of these participatory and inclusive practices. This evaluation was undertaken in 2021-22, after the release of the WGI report, with an overall focus of inquiry to learn about the factors that supported or prevented participation and inclusion within WGI. Based on these learnings, this report identifies potential considerations for future IPCC assessment report processes which can serve to strengthen the participation and inclusion of diverse authors in IPCC processes. The summary below shares insights around the impacts of the work and lessons learned from the evaluation and goes on to suggest recommendations for future assessment reports.

¹ The IPCC Code of Conduct : www.ipcc.ch/site/assets/uploads/2019/07/Code_of_Conduct.pdf

Impacts

- **Impact #1:** Generally, authors experienced a positive change in inclusion and participation between the start and end of AR6.
- **Impact #2:** The majority of authors believe that the final report was improved by the diversity of perspectives and participation.

Lessons

- **Lesson #1:** There are a number of authors who experience multiple, often intersecting barriers to participation and inclusion, particularly authors from the Global South.
- **Lesson #2:** The lack of structures and resources to support many climate scientists in the Global South contributes to inequities among authors.
- **Lesson #3:** Virtual connections and workspaces are a useful accompaniment to in-person meetings but they can't replace them. Some authors need additional supports.
- **Lesson #4:** Cultural diversity is a strength for the IPCC and there is a need to improve cross-cultural intelligence.
- **Lesson #5:** Many authors attribute the positive changes to the culture of inclusion and participation between the start and end of AR6 to strengthened relationships and the use of inclusive practices.
- **Lesson #6:** The role of CLAs is key to supporting (or preventing) collaborative relationships and inclusive practices in the chapter groups.

Recommendations

- **Recommendation #1:** Develop and/or formalize roles and knowledge transfer related to participatory and inclusive practices.
- **Recommendation #2:** Continue to recruit, train and support the CLAs considering their roles as facilitators and leaders of participatory and inclusive group practices.
- **Recommendation #3:** Continue to connect, orient and train all authors to build a strong Working Group culture of participation and inclusion.
- **Recommendation #4:** Support greater author participation and access to climate research from the Global South.
- **Recommendation #5:** Continue and strengthen feedback loops and learning about inclusion and participation.

Conclusion

Overall, this experience suggests that an intentional Working Group focus on strengthening participation and inclusion of diverse authors can support the quality and impact of IPCC assessment reports. The many learnings about participation and inclusion in WGI throughout the AR6 process offer important insights which can serve to strengthen future IPCC processes. Of particular importance is the growing understanding of the barriers to meaningful participation, and the experience of multiple barriers that some authors contend with, such as being a first-time author, a non-native English speaker, from the Global South, and/or female, and lack of time. This understanding can contribute to strategies for greater inclusion and an even stronger and more diverse report. To support this, it is recommended that future Working Groups take action to build on these opportunities through formalizing a focus on participatory and inclusive practices; supporting CLAs in their roles as facilitators and inclusive leaders; ensuring equitable gender, geographic and age/career stage representation within the Working Groups; and creating processes which aim to address systemic barriers and inequities for authors who experience intersecting challenges to participation, particularly for, but not limited to, authors from the Global South.

Photo by Jan Fuglestedt

BACKGROUND & INTRODUCTION

Working Group I (WGI) of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change is responsible for assessing the physical science of climate change, most recently contributing to the IPCC's Sixth Assessment Report (AR6) between 2018 -2021. The Working Group engaged over 230 scientists from all parts of the world who collaborated, sharing their expertise and knowledge to assess the latest knowledge on climate science and change.

From the outset of AR6, WGI identified that encouraging the participation and inclusion of diverse authors within the Working Group was a priority. The IPCC procedures state that when selecting authors and Working Group members, efforts should be made to strive for regional and gender balance, but there are currently no further guidelines for ensuring participatory and inclusive practices throughout the report drafting process.

The WGI Technical Support Unit (TSU) and Bureau recognized that a collaborative, inclusive process that maximizes the participation and contribution of all authors could positively influence the quality and impact of the final assessment report and made efforts to support this.

These efforts included setting a welcoming and supportive environment for new authors; introducing a Code of Conduct² at the first lead author meeting (LAM1, 2018); running post-LAM surveys with authors which included a range of evaluative questions about participation and inclusion; and working with [SHIFT Collaborative](#) beginning at LAM2 (2019) onwards to the end of the assessment process to provide expert support for creating an inclusive and participatory culture. Together with the Bureau and TSU, in the time surrounding LAM2, 3, and 4, SHIFT Collaborative designed resources and facilitated a series of training and dialogue opportunities around strengthening diversity, inclusion, collaboration and participatory decision-making. Authors and other Working Group members were invited to work together to strengthen a culture of collaboration and inclusion, guided by the following invitation:

How might we co-create a space that is inclusive and collaborative? Based on these learnings, this report identifies potential considerations for future assessment report processes which can serve to strengthen the participation and inclusion of diverse authors in IPCC processes.

- What does an **inclusive, collaborative culture** look like?
- **How can I personally contribute** to strengthening participation, collaboration and inclusion? What is my role or “learning edge”?

² [The IPCC Code of Conduct](http://www.ipcc.ch/site/assets/uploads/2019/07/Code_of_Conduct.pdf): www.ipcc.ch/site/assets/uploads/2019/07/Code_of_Conduct.pdf

This report, written by SHIFT Collaborative with input from the WGI TSU, **summarizes key findings and learnings from a retrospective evaluation of these participatory and inclusive practices.** This evaluation was undertaken in 2021-22, after the release of the WGI report, with an overall focus of inquiry to learn about the factors that supported or prevented participation and inclusion within WGI. Appendix III to this report summarizes the best practices for participation and inclusion. Based on these learnings, this report identifies potential considerations for future assessment report processes which can serve to strengthen the participation and inclusion of diverse authors in IPCC processes. The approach to this report is aligned with a learning and “adaptive action” framework commonly used in developmental evaluation, or “live time” evaluation. It follows these three main lines of inquiry and learning:

- **WHAT did we do?**
- **SO.... WHAT** were the results or impacts?
- **SO... WHAT** did we learn?
- **NOW WHAT** are the next steps or opportunities moving forward to adapt, improve or strengthen impacts?

Photo by Jan Fuglestvedt

METHODS

This evaluation was conducted in two main phases. The analysis and recommendations in this report reflect a synthesis of both phases.

Phase 1: Review of past author surveys

The Phase 1 evaluation, which was completed in March 2022, focused on a review of all past LAM author surveys (7 surveys in total) conducted by the TSU and SHIFT Collaborative, and the related activities and resources that were delivered to authors during the drafting of the WGI AR6 report. These surveys were sent to authors at specific times during the report drafting process, usually after or during a lead author meeting (LAM), or after specific training sessions for Coordinating Lead Authors (CLAs) or others. Surveys aimed to capture a debrief of the recent meeting and to help prepare for the next stage of the process. A list of the surveys and related data inputs for Phase I can be found in Appendix I. The resulting report from this analysis can be viewed [HERE](#).

The Phase 1 analysis identified that while a majority of authors reported a positive experience or improvement related to the inclusive culture of the Working Group, **there was a group of authors who continued to experience multiple barriers to participation and inclusion. These authors were largely first-time authors from the Global South.**

Phase 2: Survey and Focus Groups

The Phase 2 evaluation activities, which were undertaken in June-November 2022, focused on exploring the experience of authors from the Global South in more depth, as well as the role of Coordinating Lead Authors, in order to identify considerations for future IPCC processes.

The activities included a final survey of all authors (Coordinating Lead Authors - CLAs, Lead Authors - LAs, and Review Editors - REs), Chapter Scientists, Bureau and TSU members, as well as a series of focus groups. The survey questions can be found in Appendix II.

Photo by Christina @ wocintechchat.com

113 authors representing every chapter participated in the Phase 2 evaluation survey of participatory and inclusive practices. Survey respondents also represented every region as broken down in the following graph.

The following six targeted focus groups reached out to authors from the Global South (13 participants) and CLAs (8 participants) and were arranged as follows:

- One session with first-time authors from Africa
- One session with first-time authors from Asia
- One session with first-time authors from Mexico, Central and South America
- Two sessions with CLAs (two sessions were run to cover different time zones)
- A conversation with TSU and Bureau members to share and get feedback on preliminary findings and recommendations.

Limitations of Data

The survey data reviewed in Phase 1 has some limitations:

- Generally, participation in the surveys was over 50% of all authors with some exceptions, for example, when only the CLAs were surveyed. As such, we can see a diversity of experiences and opinions in the survey comments, however, we do not know how the activities affected authors that did not complete a survey or why they did not do so.
- Authors were asked to report about their demographic status “if they were willing”, so this data is not comprehensive. In LAM1 and LAM2 surveys, 6% and 1% respectively opted not to share their gender, and in the LAM3 survey this increased to 12% of respondents. The question was not asked in the final LAM4 survey. We do know that among those who did share this information, the female survey responses are within the range of overall participation in the WG (between 25 – 31%), and the response across countries likewise is representative of author participation. This suggests that generally the survey responses represent the diversity of authors, however, using a comparative by gender may not be reliable.
- The survey also asked a series of questions about barriers to participation that authors were experiencing, and these responses can provide some comparative analysis. These barriers included, for example, “being female” or “being a new author” as well as things like “lack of time”. However, respondents were able to select “this is not a problem for me” which does not tell us if the person identifies as a woman, but does not associate barriers with that, or if they do not identify as a woman.

The Phase 2 survey had two questions that were problematic and where results have been interpreted with that in mind.

- One question asked about the extent to which individual awareness and practices had changed over the course of AR6. Authors noted that this was not useful given two things: that it did not account for high levels of skills at the beginning, so an author could indicate no change in their awareness or practice and yet be highly skilled, and second that changes in inclusive practices may not have been the result of the experience with WGI.
- The other question asked authors to identify practices/resources that were used in their chapters, and to rate the extent to which these practices were impactful in terms of strengthening participation and inclusion. Some found this dual rating confusing, and a few commented that the scale was not fulsome enough to reflect their experience. It went from “a great deal” of impact to “somewhat” and authors wanted something in between.

WHAT WE DID: Activities & Resources

This section summarizes the activities and resources that were delivered by SHIFT Collaborative, the WGI TSU and Bureau between LAM2 (in person), January 2019, through LAM3 (in person), August 2019 and leading up to LAM4, Pre-LAM4 (held virtually), June-September 2020. There is also some LAM1 data included as relevant background. The activities were designed to support authors' awareness, developing skills and tools to **co-create an inclusive culture within the WG**.

Overview of Activities & Resources

From the outset, the approach was to engage all authors as voluntary learners and leaders in supporting this culture. At the same time, it was identified that Coordinating Lead Authors (CLAs) had the potential to be key influencers within their chapter groups and specific facilitation training was offered to this group. Tailored coaching was also offered to chapter groups at LAM3 and continued with several groups between LAM3 and LAM4.

WG I INCLUSIVE PRACTICE ACTIVITIES & RESOURCES

SO...WHAT WERE THE IMPACTS?

WHAT CHANGED?

This section presents the main findings on the impact of running inclusive and participatory practice training and guidance throughout the WGI drafting process. It discusses key lessons that were identified in the Phase 1 and 2 author surveys and evaluation focus groups.

Impact #1: Generally, authors experienced a positive change in inclusion and participation between the start and end of AR6.

Of the authors responding to the post LAM3 survey (n=101), **84% identified the level of participation in the WG overall as good or excellent and 87% identified the participation in their chapter groups as good or excellent.**

“Our chapter is working well; ... is engaged; ... has a good atmosphere.”

In the same LAM3 survey, **a majority of authors agreed with these practice statements:**

- There is openness about culture and difference
- Everyone is valued for their contribution
- There is respect for new ideas
- Everyone has an opportunity to speak
- We take time to get to know each other
- We use virtual platforms to connect and share materials
- Members have time to read material in advance

In the Phase 2 survey (n=113), authors' responses affirmed these assessments:

- **87% of all authors identified positive change in their awareness and personal practice of inclusion**, however a few comments suggested that some of these changes were not only a result of WGI activities.
- **77% of authors rated inclusive culture within WGI as good or excellent** in this final survey. This is an **increase of 27%** from the beginning of the AR6 process (50%).

Impact #2: The majority of authors think that the final report was improved by the diversity of perspectives and participation.

In the Phase 2 survey (n=113):

- **84 % of responding authors indicated that they thought the AR6 report was improved** either a great deal or somewhat by the diversity of perspectives and participation.
- Only 2% said the diversity and inclusion practices had NOT improved the report, and 15% were not sure.

“Participation of these diverse authors has led to the report being more relevant to all countries on the planet. There is less of a Northern-Hemisphere bias in the report than before, small islands are well covered, these are small things that however for those of us in “marginal” regions do make a difference.”

“The AR6 report devotes fully 1/3rd of its content to coverage of an increased number of regions in the world (over the AR5 report)”.

In addition, authors shared some **additional impacts or changes they observed:**

- As a result of the **proactive recruitment of new authors**, there was an increase of authors from the Global South, as well as an increase in younger authors (who were described as bringing new ideas and fresh eyes).
- Overall, authors reported **increased virtual literacy**, resources and comfort working virtually that can continue to support greater continuity, communication and collaborative work between LAMs in the future.
- Authors reported **personal impacts** including new awareness, skills and knowledge, increased confidence and expanded networks. Some of these are inherent in the process and in other cases, authors attributed the changes to the intentional inclusive practice activities which were undertaken.

“I noticed that the activities organized by WGI TSU/SHIFT Collaborative resulted in a significant change in the attitude of many CLAs from developing countries. I found that crucial to get positive changes in terms of inclusion within the chapter work where I think the inclusion problems are larger”.

SO...WHAT ARE THE LESSONS?

Systemic Barriers that Prevented Participation and Inclusion

Lesson #1: There is a number of authors who experience multiple, often intersecting barriers to participation and inclusion.

While there are a range of individual barriers that authors identify as part of their experience, there is a cluster of authors who are experiencing multiple, intersecting barriers. This contributes to a foundational inequity among these authors. In the Phase 2 evaluation survey (N=113):

- **20% of all authors identified that inclusive culture was satisfactory or poor** at the end of AR6 (4.5% rated it “poor”). While this is an improvement from the start of AR6 (36%), it suggests there is a group of authors who continue to experience or observe barriers to participation and inclusion. These authors represent all regions and genders.
- 5% of first-time authors and 4% of non-first-time said their authors experience of opportunities to participate was “not very much”.

“I am not sure of any relevant change in inclusive practices during the development of AR6. I really appreciate the role of SHIFT Collaborative in promoting inclusive practices and strategies to create inclusive environments in each chapter. However, the constant rush to make progress in the report somewhat precluded the chapter to incorporate inclusive practices in all meetings. Therefore, the more vocal members of the chapter would dominate the discussion.”

Being from the Global South was identified as a barrier for 22% of first-time authors and 18% of non-first-time authors in the final evaluation survey.

Close to half of all authors from Africa and South America identified being from the Global South was a barrier.

Individuals from this cluster of authors also experience a number of additional barriers to a greater degree than other authors:

- Authors from the Global South also identified barriers related to **being young** and **accessing technology** to a greater degree than other authors.
- In survey comments and focus groups, authors identified other barriers linked to being from the Global South such as **lack of resources and/or support in their institutions, lack of exposure to international scientific networks and processes and other cultural and/or language barriers**

Being from the Global South was identified as a barrier for 22% of first-time authors and 18% of non-first-time authors in the final evaluation survey.

“... looking at my first-time author colleagues from the Global South, there is a major challenge in understanding the norms and” expectations which are dominantly framed by a Global North science culture experience, ...”

For those who are first-time authors, identify as female and from the Global South, **there is a potential confluence of challenges** to deal within addition to the learning curve of being a first-time author.

- **Being female:** Of those who identified being from the Global South as a barrier to participation, 41% also identified being female as a barrier.
- **Caring for dependents:** 15% of first-time and 15% of all authors identified being female as a barrier. While proportionally the experience of first-time authors is identical to all authors, it is the intersectionality of multiple barriers that creates greater barriers to participation and therefore greater inequity. In this case, 32% of all authors identified **caring for dependents** as a barrier, but a much higher proportion (63%) of those who identify being female as a barrier also identify **caring for dependents** as a barrier.

The lack of structures and resources to support many climate scientists in the Global South contributes to inequities among authors.

Lesson #2: The lack of structures and resources to support many climate scientists in the Global South contributes to inequities among authors.

There were barriers identified in focus groups that may be beyond the influence of the WG and IPCC. On one hand, WGI has been successful in increasing participation of authors from the Global South to some extent, and on the other hand, authors identify a number of challenges they experience in their countries and institutions that are barriers to effective participation.

While these circumstances may be beyond the direct influence of the IPCC, some authors suggest there cannot be equal opportunity until these gaps are addressed:

- **Not being relieved of other duties.** Focus groups identified that the challenge of supporting more authors from the Global South often begins earlier with the need for greater institutional support or resources. Many authors from the Global South identified that they were not relieved of other duties to participate in the assessment process compared to other colleagues from the Global North who were. This creates inequity from the start and puts added pressures on authors from less resourced institutions to juggle their existing workload and the work of contributing to the assessment process.

“We say this work is voluntary but in reality, many of us have [to take] paid leave to participate.”

- **Lack of exposure to international conferences and networks.** Authors also identified that many southern institutions lack budgets to support participation in larger international conferences or learning events. This limits the international exposure, networks and awareness of these authors that can create a disadvantage when participating in the IPCC where many authors have built previous connections and expertise based on participating and interactions at such events.

“No one from (country name) can afford to go to the big conferences so we lack the connections that others have coming into IPCC.”

- **Lack of access to paywalled research papers.** The lack of funding to access research literature is another challenge for many authors from the Global South participating in IPCC. Authors commented on the lack of institutional budgets to access libraries and publications behind paywalls and having to wait months for free sources to be available.
- **Lack of regional peer reviewed research literature.** Some focus group participants from the Global South identified the lack of peer reviewed research from their regions as a challenge which impacts equitable participation and representation in the assessment. These authors suggested that greater flexibility regarding the use of grey literature and overall greater investment in scientific research from the Global South could help to address these inequities.

While the recruitment and selection of authors from the Global South has improved overall, several authors spoke about the pressure and responsibility of being a “lone voice” such as being “the only woman” or the “only one from my region”. There is a **desire to see more equitable gender, geographic and age/career stage representation**. However, in focus group sessions, several authors identified that this is often impeded by **structural and political challenges**:

- Some authors noted that **regional recruitment and nominations** by “Focal Points” are sometimes political and oriented around seniority more than strengthening diversity. By contrast, others shared that in their countries, Focal Points were leading events to raise awareness of opportunities to participate in the IPCC and being intentional about recruiting more diverse authors. In general, these authors want to see additional avenues for nomination, a focus on equity criteria, and earlier promotion of the relevant opportunities.

“Focal point and selection of authors at a national level is a very serious problem for representation of the Global South and elsewhere. We need to find a different way.”

Finally, these authors also identified the **lack of preparation and sufficient orientation** as factors that limited their participation. Focus group participants consistently called for a more formal and in-depth orientation to support clear understandings of roles, expectations and the assessment process. Enhanced orientation, ensuring greater support from host country institutions and greater clarity on how to prepare were named as opportunities that could support more fulsome participation. This could include preparatory time to develop English language skills, review of past reports, and potentially attending an international event in advance to develop stronger networks with other scientific colleagues from other regions.

Practices that Prevented Participation and Inclusion

Lesson # 3: Virtual connections and workspaces are a useful accompaniment to in-person meetings but they can't replace them. Some authors need additional support.

While CLAs were encouraged from the beginning of AR6 to engage their chapter members virtually between LAMs, this approach became imperative with the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic. The TSU provided guidance documents and resource support, researched various platforms and ran a purely virtual LAM4 (and pre-LAM activities). SHIFT Collaborative offered several training sessions and resources to support the facilitation of inclusive and participatory environments online.

This switch, combined with other pressures from the COVID-19 situation (such as working from home and pressures on authors' own research activities), exacerbated the stress for authors who were learning new ways of working. However, it is difficult to know from the LAM4 feedback in particular to what extent this context affected overall feedback about the authors' experience of the assessment process. Some of the LAM4 feedback (n=97) includes:

- On a very practical level, chapter groups were now straddling multiple time zones to find appropriate times to meet, which introduced a level of fatigue and inconvenience for some authors, depending on where they were located. Many authors, particularly female authors, experienced increased pressures related to child and family care during this time. In several cases, it also required sub-groups of authors to meet asynchronously rather than as a whole group together.
- Activities which previously would have been undertaken together in person now required groups to switch to the use of virtual, digital platforms. Inequities related to internet or digital access became apparent and presented challenges for several chapter groups. Some authors felt that it also added barriers to non-English speakers and reduced those voices even further.
- Notwithstanding author's overall preference for working in person (57% reported virtual meetings were either "not at all inclusive" or "less inclusive" than in person in the LAM4 survey), there were some who identified the virtual space increased their participation (for example by being able to watch session recordings or use the chat).
- There was appreciation for the guides and lessons about virtual meetings that were offered, and for CLAs that implemented additional virtual tools and approaches to support inclusion. The experience with virtual meetings and the guidance documents and resources provided by the TSU and SHIFT Collaborative supported increased skills and comfort with technology, which will be useful in a future, post COVID-19 context to support more efficient, inclusive chapter work between in-person meetings.

The Phase 2 Retrospective Evaluation survey responses (n =113) sum up this situation well:

- **72% of all authors identified that virtual meetings had some degree of negative impact** (either a great deal or somewhat). This was named as a contributing factor for lack of interpersonal connections, difficulty participating in discussions, poor timing of discussions and the lack of appropriate internet capacity or programs.
- **Conversely, 44% of all authors rated the virtual meetings as having an overall positive impact.** For these authors the virtual meetings saved time, supported on-going child-care commitments, could be held more often and for some the virtual context facilitated increased participation that they say would not have happened at an in-person meeting.

- **Lack of access to technology creates inequity.** Access to technology is one of the barriers often experienced by authors from the Global South to a greater degree than authors in other regions. This suggests that ongoing use of virtual ways of working will need to find ways to create equal access for this group of authors or it could serve to further isolate, rather than connect.

Lesson # 4: Cultural diversity is a strength for the IPCC and there is a need to improve cross-cultural intelligence.

In the LAM3 survey (n = 101), 45% of authors named **differences in cultural ways of working or interacting with others** as an ongoing barrier to their participation. Many, but not all, of these authors also identify English fluency as a barrier (totalling 34% of all responses). This suggests that there is a larger group of authors who see strengthening cross cultural intelligence as a means to improve participation.

The “mini dialogues” hosted by SHIFT Collaborative during some of the LAMs (see graphic on page 12) were the main place where working across cultures was discussed and explored during the WGI report process (other topics included unconscious bias, diversity, difference and power). These dialogues generally attracted approximately 35-40 authors during each LAM. These participants represented diverse cultures and geographies and were generally already informed or were experiencing barriers to participation in some fashion.

Authors’ verbal feedback on the mini-dialogue sessions was generally positive, indicating appreciation for the opportunity to reflect, share and learn from each other. They also voiced appreciation for the practical tips and tools on cultural communication norms and cross-cultural groups dynamics. Given the number of authors naming cross-cultural communication as a barrier to participation, cultural intelligence resources and training could be a high impact area for strengthening inclusion in the future.

In the evaluation survey (n=113), tools and approaches to support cultural awareness were rated the lowest uptake of all the approaches that chapters used to support inclusion and participation. This highlights both a gap and an opportunity.

“In my culture we defer to elders and those with seniority. This was pretty much everyone in my chapter.”

“In my culture we wait to be invited to speak, so if my CLA did not call on me I would not be participating well”

“I felt left out because I could not grasp the humour and references people were making.”

Practices that Supported Inclusion & Participation

Lesson # 5: Many authors attribute the positive change to the culture of inclusion and participation between the start and end of AR6 to strengthened relationships and use of inclusive practices.

A majority of authors identified that the training and resources provided **strengthened their skills and knowledge related to inclusion and participatory decision-making, however, this work competes with the time demands of chapter and cross chapter work.**

Short plenary presentations often included rapid, interactive polling which indicated that many authors were paying more attention to their own personal attitudes and practices to support inclusion. For example, authors identified these early changes in the closing poll (N=130) after the first week of working with inclusive practices during LAM2:

- 82% of those who voted thought there had been an increase in awareness about diversity, difference and power over the week.
- 62% indicated they had adjusted their own practices in some way during the week.

In the Phase 2 Evaluation survey authors identified that **a focus on relationship building increased their own and others' participation.**

“The combination of getting to know each other and continual reinforcement of inclusive practice by SHIFT Collaborative/TSU were both key to the improved participation.”

“As authors got to know each other and understand that they were there and valued for their specific areas of expertise (reinforced by positive messages and training on inclusion from the bureau/TSU/SHIFT Collaborative) they formed a close and supportive team which facilitated inclusive behaviours.”

“At the beginning we did not know our colleagues personally so were more inclined (if unconsciously) to view them through stereotypes relating to their countries of origin. Towards the end I think as we knew each other better, this played much less of a role.”

The role and support of the TSU was also acknowledged in Phase 2 Evaluation survey comments as critical in creating and facilitating a supportive environment:

“TSU was absolutely wonderful: warm, charming, helpful, smart, talented, cheerful, empathic, funny and hardworking.”

“TSU and Bureau did a great job of reminding us of inclusive practices.”

“(TSU member’s name) support in our chapter was fundamental.”

Authors identified **changes to their individual practice**, such as increased awareness of cultural biases and greater confidence to participate, as additional factors supporting inclusion. In the LAM3 survey (n=101), they rated a variety of practices as contributing “a great deal” to inclusion in their chapters, including:

- Use of resources on participatory and inclusive approaches
- Respect for new ideas
- Opportunity to speak
- Use of virtual platforms
- Working in pairs
- Everyone’s contribution was valued
- Asking questions to understand
- Making time to get to know each other

Photo by Alvaro Reyes

In the same survey, authors also identified these elements of inclusive culture as needing more ongoing attention:

- More work in pairs and small groups
- Asking questions to understand
- Willingness to balance power and address unconscious bias
- Sharing the air-time
- Speaking slowly
- Evaluating our process
- Use of group agreements and rules of productive virtual meetings
- Use of the resources and tools on the DSM

At the end of LAM3, 64% of authors surveyed (n=101) felt that the inclusion and participatory practices work should be continued:

“Excellent sessions and helpful information”

“I wish the definition of “consensus” - agree/reservations/stand aside/block - had been explained before LAM1.”

“The consensus building leaflet has been useful and widely adopted in our chapter. This is the kind of concrete action that we need more of.”

“Please offer these sessions on their own and not at the same time as our meetings so more can attend”

“The cultural awareness session helped me understand the differences between eastern and western communication styles and that has helped me in my chapter”

“Yes, yes, yes! We are still a long way from being inclusive and it is easy to lapse back in our behaviour”

While the majority of respondents were supportive of continuing this work, 28% were not sure if these practices should be continued and 8% indicated they should not. Many of those who were “not sure” indicated in comments that their primary concern was balancing time needed for the work with the time that inclusive practices require; however, there may be more to understand from this group of authors who are “not sure” if the focus on inclusive practice should continue.

For example, it would be helpful to understand if they saying this because their chapter was working well, or because the activities were not useful for improving inclusion in their chapter. In addition, it would be helpful to better understand the demographics of these respondents to analyse the role that gender, career phase, and geography play in people's perceptions and experience of inclusion.

These findings were echoed in the Phase 2 Evaluation survey, where one author pointed out that the shift in culture was both good and bad, in that as participation increased, the complexity of managing diverse inputs grew:

"We have spent considerable time and effort to be inclusive. This makes the writing aspects of our chapter more complicated, as almost all authors are contributing but the assembly is quite complex."

"Yes, but it can't be at the expense of getting the job done."

"I think plenty has been done already and this is not the only, or most important, priority for our time right now."

"Useless activity."

The role of Coordinating Lead Authors (CLAs) is key to supporting (or preventing) collaborative relationships and inclusive practices in the chapter groups.

Lesson #6: The role of Coordinating Lead Authors (CLAs) is key to supporting (or preventing) collaborative relationships and inclusive practices in the chapter groups.

CLAs have a challenging role that requires a diverse skill set. Participants of the CLA Focus groups spoke to the diversity and pressures of the CLA role. On the one hand, CLAs are leading subject matter experts in their field, and on the other hand, they are also responsible for being team managers and facilitators of participation and group decision-making. While CLAs are often recruited for their scientific experience, many authors have suggested that team and group management skills are equally, if not more, critical to this role and should be highlighted in selection criteria.

“CLAs need to be recruited for both management experience and facilitation.”

“CLAs need a mindset around “humble leadership” that supports others to be involved rather than having to be the boss or be right.”

Authors with concerns about inclusion and participation in their chapter groups often attribute the situation to coordination/facilitation skills.

Various surveys allowed for authors to provide written comments if desired on their barriers to participation. The list below identifies some feedback on the importance of inclusive facilitation within chapter meetings. The skills of CLAs and their ability to encourage inclusion, compared to those who did not make this effort, was a common theme in authors' comments.

“I know of 3 chapters that are struggling where CLAs still dominate.”

“It is still common for a few to dominate discussions. Our CLA needs help to better engage those from other cultures.”

“We need outside facilitators, or coaches to observe (for an hour) and assess our chapter functioning.”

“Between a lot of new authors from different backgrounds and a poor chair our chapter meetings are a waste of time.”

“(Our CLA) was amazing and worked hard to draw out quieter folks”

“I am not great at jumping in, I need to be asked, and my CLA worked intentionally to pull me into the discussion.”

CLA facilitation training is an effective way to increase inclusive group practices. Some CLAs have new, demonstrated facilitation skills and tools to support inclusion.

Authors often look to the CLAs to support the inclusive culture of chapter groups. And when groups are not functioning effectively, many authors see more skilled facilitation as the answer. This is exemplified in the following LAM1 survey comments:

“CLAs need to pay attention to their chapter dynamics and ensure integration of the whole chapter team.”

their chapter and that they should make a strong effort to try to engage all LAs in discussions. Objective facilitation would help.”

The CLA training at LAM2 on Core Facilitation Skills & Tools included topics such as group dynamics, ice breakers, relationship building, facilitation tools and approaches for group discussion. A post survey of CLAs indicated that 82% had used new tools or approaches during LAM2. At the LAM3 training CLAs named a number of inclusive tools or approaches they had used either during LAM2 or between LAM2 and LAM3, such as:

Photo by Jan Fuglestedt

- Socializing together
- Using “rounds” to gather input from all, Paraphrasing, Summarizing, inviting people to comment, Holding back my own comments, Use of the “bicycle rack” (a space where outstanding issues are parked for attention later)
- Being more perceptive of others body language/expressions, changing seating
- Encourage post-meeting feedback via email
- Entire chapter takes responsibility for each section, rotating the chair/facilitator
- Small groups to bring ideas/proposals back to whole group (used online as well)
- Adding video to online meetings
- Using SharePoint for all documents (a platform useable from all countries)
- Holding online meetings twice in the day to allow for different time zones.
- Change of perspective, check-ins, break out groups, individual speaking time, group agreement around norms, awareness of the stages of group development.

Awareness and skills related to participatory and consensus decision-making are important tools for CLAs to facilitate within their chapter groups.

In a CLA training session held just before LAM3, many CLAs identified that their biggest challenge was participation of all authors including engaging authors in discussion and in doing the work. After the LAM3 CLA training on consensus decision-making, a majority of CLAs identified that the consensus tip sheet, hand signals and a number of other approaches or tools were useful:

“very helpful session”

“useful examples and materials”

“liked learning what other CLAs are doing/sharing ideas”

The LAM3 survey (n=101) showed that 87% of authors rated chapter inclusion and participation as either good or excellent, supporting the positive feedback from CLAs regarding their use of new approaches. The extent to which the CLA training is influencing this, and other factors that may be at play, is not totally clear, however it appears that the CLA training is one contributing factor.

“In my chapter we do not have inclusion problems, and the 2 CLAs always make sure everybody participates to the discussions. However, not all chapters work this well, so it is good to keep on the participatory training.”

Ongoing coaching, peer learning and CLA training sessions can provide important support.

Many CLAs identified the benefits of having a dedicated space for peer learning to share chapter group process tips and challenges. For example, if there are authors that are struggling to participate, this needs to be flagged early and possible support can be identified through discussion and troubleshooting with peers.

“The connection with other CLAs was so helpful. I wish it had happened earlier on for me”.

In addition to the role of CLAs, some suggested that WG Co-Chairs could play an increased role in supporting authors' readiness, understanding of process and expectations in the chapter. This was raised as a way to reduce the amount that CLAs were responsible for.

Tailored coaching or external facilitation may be useful to problem solve specific challenges within chapter groups.

Chapter coaching for CLAs was offered on a voluntary basis from LAM2, however, it took some time for CLAs to get to know SHIFT Collaborative and build some trust in the process. Several reached out for conversations during LAM3 and two others had some light coaching between LAM3 and Pre-LAM4.

There was no follow-up to understand if or how this coaching affected chapter functioning.

There is also no formal assessment of chapter inclusive practices. While some CLAs implemented feedback polls for their members, this is an internal practice and not generally shared with the

TSU. Likewise, author surveys that ask them to rate participation in their chapter group are anonymous, so there is not a clear sense of how each chapter group is doing, or which groups might need additional support.

Photo by Jan Fuglestedt

Some authors have made suggestions that dedicated coaching support and/or external facilitation be available for/during chapter meetings, and/or that the TSU conduct assessments of chapter inclusive practices. To date however, the TSU has opted for a voluntary process. It may be useful to explore some kind of “middle ground” approach that preserves choice and makes chapter supports more accessible.

“More of the same, plus in-chapter (during chapter meetings) coaching and facilitation would be great.”

“I am interested in measuring how these interventions are impacting the process.”

NOW WHAT?

Themes and Recommendations for Moving Forward

A great deal has been learned about participation and inclusion in WGI throughout the AR6 process. The following recommendations highlight opportunities to build on these learnings in future IPCC processes. They highlight key themes and recommendations that have emerged from WGI surveys and focus groups, as well as SHIFT Collaborative's experience with the Working Group and analysis of this evaluation data.

Recommendation #1: Develop and/or formalize roles and knowledge transfer related to participatory and inclusive practices.

Engage in knowledge transfer in advance of AR7. There have been significant learnings about the role of participatory and inclusive practices within WGI that affirms that the “process” deeply impacts the final assessment report “product”. It is recommended that these learnings be shared and socialized with future Bureaus, TSUs and other IPCC bodies in order to build on these learnings, address gaps, and continue to improve equitable and inclusive participation of diverse authors in future processes.

Formalize work on participatory practices and inclusion as a role for the TSU and Bureau. Document the roles and functions that have been key for the TSU and Bureau in supporting participatory and inclusive practices during the AR6 process. Develop a mechanism to ensure that this is part of succession planning and ensure that this work is part of the Bureau and TSU's mandate. Training for Bureau members and TSU representatives would strengthen their capacity to address these aspects more substantively.

Continue to work with external expert partners. As an external agent, SHIFT Collaborative has been able to draw attention to things and bring fresh “outside” eyes and ideas to the work of building a more participatory and inclusive Working Group culture. Continue to work with external agencies who specialize in participatory process to support training and coaching for Working Groups moving forward.

Recommendation #2: Recruit, train and support the CLAs considering their roles as facilitators and leaders of participatory and inclusive group practices.

Recruit CLAs for the role. CLAs should be recruited with clear expectations for their role. This should include team management experience, group facilitation skills, and commitment to the underlying principles of inclusive practice in addition to their subject matter expertise.

Continue and strengthen CLA training and support. Continue to offer training, toolkits, and ongoing peer learning structures between CLAs, with particular emphasis on cross-cultural intelligence, facilitating cross-cultural teams, and participatory decision-making processes. Start CLA training in these topics early through intensive training in advance of LAM1.

Consider if there is a need for a specific CLA role, or another role to support first-time authors in particular. Consider opportunities and appropriate mechanisms for CLAs to flag when an author is struggling and get support from TSU and/or Bureau.

Recommendation #3: Continue to connect, orient and train all authors to build a strong Working Group culture of participation and inclusion.

Utilize plenary sessions, shared resources, and ongoing training to build Working Group culture and practice. Continue to incorporate plenary presentations related to building a participatory and inclusive culture across the Working Group. Make resources on these themes available, along with ongoing training and dialogue opportunities for authors to engage in peer learning throughout the assessment report process.

Deliver a robust orientation for all authors. Improve the orientation process through an intensive “orientation bootcamp” so all authors have a better understanding of the scoping and drafting process and the various roles and expectations and can participate more fully. As part of this orientation, create space for relationship building and initial training in participatory and inclusive practices, with particular emphasis on working collaboratively in cross-cultural groups.

“The investment of a day in advance to train everyone and meet each other would save hours of time and energy in the chapters”.

Increase support for first-time authors. Consider additional support for first-time authors such as a buddy or mentor system, Communities of Practice, and support from regional Bureau co-chairs.

Recommendation #4: Support greater author participation, and facilitate access to and the assessment of literature, from the Global South.

Strengthen the access and inclusion of literature, particularly from the Global South. Work with institutions, regional and country governments and the IPCC to support authors from the Global South to have access to all relevant literature, including paywalled publications, and for regional research to be translated into English and included as part of the assessment.

Strengthen access to resources for authors in the Global South. Work with author institutions and country governments to support equitable participation in the IPCC process as part of their work; provide support for the use of appropriate technology.

Diversify and enhance representation and author nomination activities. Develop a strategy and criteria to continue to increase regional, age, gender and career-stage representation amongst participants of the assessment process. Work with country governments and the IPCC to raise awareness of opportunities to participate in IPCC activities.

Recommendation #5: Continue and strengthen feedback loops and learning about inclusion and participation.

Continue to evaluate participation and inclusion through surveys and other tools. Ensure continued learning about different groups' experiences and continue to focus on both process and impact/results. Share these results with Working Group members and encourage developmental learning and adaptations based on Working Group feedback. Modify survey questions to ensure appropriate demographic data can consistently be included in the analysis.

Formalize chapter feedback: Develop mechanisms to evaluate inclusion and participatory practices within chapter groups and support continuous improvement.

CONCLUSION

Overall, this experience suggests that an intentional focus on strengthening participation and inclusion of diverse authors can support the quality and impact of IPCC assessment reports. The many learnings about participation and inclusion in WGI throughout the AR6 process offer important insights which can serve to strengthen future IPCC processes.

Of particular importance is the growing understanding of the barriers to meaningful participation, and the experience of multiple barriers that some authors contend with, such as being a first-time author, a non-native English speaker, from the Global South, and/or female, and lack of time. This understanding can contribute to strategies for greater inclusion and an even stronger and more diverse report. To support this, it is recommended that future Working Groups take action to build on these opportunities through formalizing a focus on participatory and inclusive practices; supporting CLAs in their roles as facilitators and inclusive leaders; ensuring equitable gender, geographic and age/career stage representation within the Working Groups; and creating processes which aim to address systemic barriers and inequities for authors who experience intersecting challenges to participation, particularly for, but not limited to authors from the Global South.

APPENDIX I:

SUMMARY OF ALL SURVEYS AND DATA SOURCES

- WGI AR6 LAM1 Feedback Survey
- CLA Training Feedback LAM2
- WGI AR6 LAM2 Feedback Survey Summary
- CLA Survey Report post LAM2
- LAM2 Reflection Notes for TSU by SHIFT Collaborative
- CLA Check In (verbal) and Feedback Form (survey) Summaries from LAM3
- WGI AR6 LAM3 Feedback Survey and Summary
- Comparison Report of LAM2, LAM3, and SHIFT Collaborative Survey Responses
- LAM3 Reflection Notes for TSU by SHIFT Collaborative
- WGI AR6 Pre-LAM4 Feedback Survey Summary
- Retrospective Evaluation -All Author Survey June 2022
- Retrospective Evaluation -Focus Groups:
 - 2 x CLAs
 - 3 x Authors from Global South: South America, Africa, Asia
 - 1 x TSU/Bureau

APPENDIX II:

QUESTIONS FROM EVALUATION PHASE 2 SURVEY

PART 1: ABOUT YOU

1. Your Region (select one)
 - Region I: Africa
 - Region II: Asia
 - Region III: South America
 - Region IV: North America, Central America, and the Caribbean
 - Region V: South-West Pacific
 - Region VI: Europe
2. Chapter group during AR6:
 - List: 1-12, Atlas
3. Your primary role:
 - Coordinating Lead Author (all parts, 1 - 5)
 - Lead Author (all BUT Part 5 CLA)
 - Bureau member (all BUT Part 3 & 5)
 - Review Editor (all BUT Part 5)
 - TSU (all BUT Part 3 & 5)
 - Chapter Scientist (all BUT Part 5)
4. Were you a 1st time IPCC Assessment Report author for AR6?
 - Yes
 - No

PART 2: INDIVIDUAL PRACTICE AND EXPERIENCE

5. To what extent would you say that your awareness about diversity and inclusion in the context of producing a high-quality assessment has increased over the course of AR6?

A great deal Somewhat Don't Know Not very much Not at all

6. To what extent would you say that your **personal practices or ways of working with others** to support diversity and inclusion have improved over the course of AR6?

A great deal Somewhat Don't Know Not very much Not at all

7. To what extent would you say that you **experienced equitable opportunities to participate and a sense of being included** over the course of AR6?

A great deal Somewhat Don't Know Not very much Not at all

Comments.

8. What **barriers to full and positive participation** did you experience, if any? (with each subquestion followed by a response options: 'major barrier for me', 'minor barrier for me' 'not a barrier for me', 'N/A')

- Lack of fluency in English
- Being female
- Being transgender or gender diverse
- Being a person of color
- Being from the Global South
- Being a younger scholar
- Responsibilities for caring for dependents
- Technology or internet challenges
- Timing of Meetings
- Other (please specify)

Comments.

9. In hindsight, as you look back at AR6, what would have been helpful to you personally to address any barriers and strengthen your participation and inclusion?

PART 3: INCLUSIVE PRACTICE IN YOUR CHAPTER GROUP

10. Which of the following inclusive practices were used in your chapter and for each you select, to what extent did it contribute to participation and inclusion? (select all that apply) Include a rating system for each:

A great deal Somewhat Not at all Don't Know

- There was openness about culture and difference
- Everyone was valued for their contribution
- There was respect for new ideas
- Everyone had an opportunity to speak
- We took time to get to know each other

- We used virtual platforms to connect and share materials
- Members (mostly) had time to read material in advance
- We worked in pairs and small groups
- We asked questions to understand each other
- There was a willingness to balance power and address unconscious bias
- We shared the air time
- We tried to speak slowly
- Evaluated our process together
- Used group agreements and/or rules for productive virtual meetings
- Used resources on the DSM
- There was effort to build cross-cultural awareness

Comments.

11. Can you share an **example of something that changed** (positive and/or negative) and what you think contributed to that?

PART 4: INCLUSIVE CULTURE WITHIN WGI

12. Generally, how would you rate the inclusive practices and culture **within WGI** as a **whole** at the beginning and at the end of AR6?

At the beginning:

Excellent *Good* *Satisfactory* *Poor* *Don't Know*

At the end:

Excellent *Good* *Satisfactory* *Poor* *Don't Know*

13. Can you share an **example of something that changed** (positive and/or negative) and what you think contributed to that?

14. To what extent do you think that COVID and the **move to working virtually** (Spring 2020) had a positive impact on inclusive practice and culture **overall in the WG?**

A great deal *Somewhat* *Don't Know* *Not very much* *Not at all*

Comments.

15. To what extent do you think that covid and the **move to working virtually** (about May 2020) had a negative impact on inclusive practice and culture **overall in the WG?**

A great deal Somewhat Don't Know Not very much Not at all

Comments.

16. The process throughout AR6 included a growing focus on integration and co-ordination efforts beyond the chapter assessments. As you look back on these **cross-chapter efforts**, please share any specific situations that stand out for you as **working well, or needing improvement from the perspective of participation and inclusion?**

17. In hindsight, as you look back at AR6, what **advice would you give to the TSU and Bureau** about their role and what they could do to support an inclusive culture within WGI?

18. To what extent do you think that the **quality of the final report** was strengthened by the inclusion of diverse perspectives and expertise?

A great deal Somewhat Don't Know Not very much Not at all

Comments.

19. In your opinion, **how important is it** for future IPCC Assessment processes to focus on strengthening participation and inclusion of diverse perspectives and expertise?

A great deal Somewhat Don't Know Not very much Not at all

Why or why not?

Thank you for your time to support our continued learning and improvement of inclusive practices! If you were a 1st time author during AR6, we would particularly like to better understand your experience of participation and inclusion and invite you to participate in a follow up conversation in September.

Are you interested in joining a conversation focused on better understanding and learning from the experiences of first-time authors?

Yes/No, If yes: (name and contact)

APPENDIX III: SHIFT RESOURCES

LAM2

- CLA Toolkit: Facilitating Participatory & Inclusive Group Process
- Resources: Tools and Techniques for Working in Diverse Groups
- Resources: Working with Unconscious Bias
- Resources for Working Across Cultures

LAM3

- CLA Toolkit: Facilitating Consensus Decision-Making
- Consensus Decision-Making Tip Sheet
- Understanding Cultural Values in Intercultural Groups
- Resources: Tools to Support Working with Conflict

Pre-LAM4

- CLA Resource: Tips for Facilitating Virtual Meetings
- CLA Resource: Resources for Virtual Team Building
- CLA Resource: Template for Leading Groups Online
- Etiquette for Inclusive & Productive Virtual Meetings
- Building Group Agreements within IPCC WG I

APPENDIX IV:

AUTHORS VISION AND PRACTICE SUGGESTIONS

These are the authors aspirations for their inclusive practice generated during LAM2:

Mindsets

- We are aware of the differences between our culture, work styles, temperaments.
- We can stand in the shoes of another
- We are open minded
- We listen
- We are flexible/adaptive
- We value everyone as a thinker -not just for their specialty area
- We acknowledge the power imbalance around roles and privilege
- We uncover and address our unconscious biases

Practices

- We raise hands, use rounds, share the air time-there is a process for calling on people
- We speak slowly and clearly
- Leaders model inclusive practices in speaking and in making assignments
- We use “horizontal” dialogue (<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10588-015-9201-1>)
- We practice common ground rules
- We take time for 1-1 discussions
- We adapt our group processes to accommodate diverse cultural norms and communication styles

Structures

- CLAs are trained in group facilitation
- Everyone has access to training and resources for group collaboration and inclusion
- We have scheduled time for social connections -over meals, etc.
- We create common ground rules
- We incorporate ground rules for in person meetings and teleconferences such as speaking slowly, staying succinct, documenting
- We use google docs, slack and other tech tools to support communication between meetings

Authors suggestions from the end of LAM 3 and in the Phase 2 Evaluation are summarized below by theme.

Inclusive Practice Training and Supports

- Start LAMs one day earlier and have a meeting to orient all new authors and let them meet each other.
- Conduct CLA training in advance of LAM 1 to strengthen chapter group process and facilitation.
- Provide more inclusive practice training in advance of the first LAM. Include topics such as: unconscious bias, ground rules for meetings for all authors, communications training to support sharing diverse opinions respectfully.
- Ensure that the Bureau and TSU also have access to training at the beginning of the AR process. Include those who might be chairing a cross chapter discussion.
- Provide mandatory training for CLAs and all authors between in-person meetings to save time when working together; offer webinars between LAMs
- Focus inclusive practice trainings within chapters to go beyond information offered in plenary sessions.
- Keep tools practical: e.g., the Consensus Decision-making tip sheet has been well used.
- Offer an objective facilitator to work with CLAs on planning. This person could be available for troubleshooting and could visit the chapter to assess and offer ideas to support chapter participation.
- Conduct polls or surveys to get feedback by chapter and evaluate how chapters are doing. This could be for CLAs only to improve their practice, or it could be open to TSU as well.
- Convene more in person sessions, supported by regular virtual meetings.
- Support more social activities and cross-cultural sharing events early in the process.
- Host a meeting or Community of Practice for CLAs who identify as women to connect and support each other.
- Develop a Community of Practice for all CLAs to share what works between chapters.
- Have a mechanism to identify challenging group or chapter dynamics and provide facilitation support to help with difficult situations.

Language and Cultural Awareness

- Support English language training.
- Provide cross cultural orientations for authors prior to LAM 1. Include more information on diverse cultural communication norms and approaches, etc.
- Provide language interpretation.
- Review and adapt SHIFT Collaborative training to model cross cultural process/practices.

Recruitment and Chapter Structure

- Include more women and authors from Global South.
- Ensure that CLA teams represent more than one gender.
- Issues of workload and burn out were named by several authors and others observed that the process was not sustainable, in particular for authors from southern, smaller Universities. Suggestions included paying for a portion of authors time and also intervening to ensure Universities were offered supports and leave time for authors.
- Provide clear expectations for new authors and orient them to the roles/expectations of others.
- Balance career-stage representation in Chapter groups. Role of IPCC
- Continue to provide additional supports and training for post report communications.
- Support CLAs to integrate and be accountable for inclusive practices.
- Support Bureau leadership and role modelling of inclusive practices.

